

1 **Behavioral interventions for vaccination uptake: A systematic review and meta-analysis**

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18

19 **Abstract**

20

21 **Background**

22 Human behavior and more specifically behavioral insight-based approaches to vaccine uptake
23 have often been overlooked. While there have been a few narrative reviews indexed in Medline
24 on behavioral interventions to increase vaccine uptake, to our knowledge, none have been
25 systematic reviews and meta-analyses covering not just high but also low-and-middle income
26 countries.

27

28 **Methods**

29 We included 613 studies from the Medline database in our systematic review and meta-analysis
30 categorizing different behavioral interventions in to 9 domains: education campaigns, on-site
31 vaccination, incentives, free vaccination, institutional recommendation, provider
32 recommendation, reminder and recall, message framing, and vaccine champion. Additionally,
33 considering that there is variability in the acceptance of vaccines among different populations,
34 we assessed studies from both high-income countries (HIC) and low- to middle-income countries
35 (LMIC), separately.

36

37 **Findings**

38 Our results show that behavioral interventions can considerably improve vaccine uptake in most
39 settings. All domains that we examined improved vaccine uptake with the highest effect size
40 associated with Provider Recommendation (OR: 3.4 (95%CI: 2.5-4.6); Domain: motivation) and
41 Onsite vaccination (OR: 2.9 (95%CI: 2.3-3.7); Domain: practical issues). Although the number
42 of studies from LMIC was smaller, the quality of studies was similar across HIC and LMIC.
43 However, effect sizes were different.

44

45 **Interpretation**

46 Our findings indicate that “provider recommendation” and “on-site vaccination” along with other
47 behavioral interventions can be employed to increase vaccination rates globally.

48

49

50 **Introduction**

51 Vaccines are one of the most effective and cost-effective tools available for preventing infectious
52 diseases and save millions of lives each year.^{1,2} However, vaccine uptake is variable across
53 different populations and vaccines. Globally, progress towards equitable vaccine coverage has
54 been uneven.

55 There are multiple determinants of under-vaccination including inadequate supply of vaccines,
56 and lack of awareness and education about vaccination. While some of the barriers to vaccine
57 uptake are structural, others are related to human behavior.^{3,4} Behavioral science, which uses an
58 interdisciplinary approach to systematically study human behavior, offers promise in designing
59 interventions that use the behavioral and social determinants of vaccination to increase vaccine
60 uptake. Behavioral science as a field has advanced significantly in the past decade, however,
61 behavioral insights have been applied unevenly to immunization efforts.

62 While there have been a few narrative reviews on behavioral interventions to increase vaccine
63 uptake, none have been systematic reviews and meta-analyses covering not just high but also
64 low-and-middle income countries (LMICs).^{5,6}

65 We present results from the first comprehensive systematic review and meta-analysis of the
66 literature on behavioral insights-based interventions to increase vaccine uptake. This review aims
67 to synthesize the evidence on which behavioral interventions work, and which could work to
68 inform interventions at all levels of the vaccine delivery process and increase equitable vaccine
69 coverage in LMICs. We assessed all articles published between 1990 and 2020 as described in
70 methods and material. Our primary outcome of interest was the effects of behavioral
71 interventions on vaccine uptake. We also considered articles discussing the effects of behavioral
72 interventions on vaccine knowledge, attitude, and intent.

73 We classified interventions into nine domains: education campaigns, on-site vaccination,
74 incentives, free vaccination, institutional recommendation, provider recommendation, reminder
75 and recall, message framing, and vaccine champion. For studies that address multiple domains,
76 we classified them under multiple domains.

77

78 **Methods**

79 Search strategy

80 We searched the database Medline on the platform Ovid, using the Medline All segment, which
81 includes non-Medline PubMed records. While we considered searching additional bibliographic
82 databases – in particular, Embase and PsycINFO – we decided that a comprehensive search
83 strategy in a single database with robust subject indexing was sufficiently sensitive. Additional
84 search on Embase did not add to the sensitivity of the search using the identified seminal studies
85 (described below). Relevant material from journals not indexed in Medline (such as *Journal of*
86 *Economic Behavior and Organization*, *Behavioral Science and Policy*, and *Health*
87 *Communication*) was identified through expert knowledge and citation chaining.

88 We tested multiple preliminary searches. While the part of the search about vaccination was not
89 complex to design, two methodological decision points emerged: how to operationalize the
90 concept of behavioral approaches and whether to include a third concept (the outcome of
91 vaccination uptake, a broader set of outcomes including vaccine knowledge, attitudes, and
92 practices as well as uptake, or a study design filter for intervention studies).

93 To test different iterations of the search strategy, we identified 43 seminal studies on behavioral
94 interventions for vaccine uptake. Of these, 39 were available in Medline, and we used these to
95 evaluate the sensitivity of different iterations of the search strategy. We also noted the screening
96 workload of different approaches. Some of the approaches we considered are presented in the
97 table below. Some of the approaches we considered are presented in Supplemental Table 1 with
98 complete details in Appendix A of the Supplement. Operationalization III performed the best out
99 of these approaches and was the basis for the final version of the search.

100 Ultimately, we added restored two of the behavior terms from Operationalization II to
101 Operationalization III. With respect to the final validation set of 39 records available in Medline,
102 this approach to the behavioral concepts retrieved 35 of them, or 90%. The whole search strategy
103 retrieved 33 (85%) of the validation set. Its three concepts (vaccines, intervention studies, and
104 behavioral approaches) are operationalized with keywords and controlled vocabulary terms.

105 Documents dated prior to 1990 and documents that solely focused on animals without
106 considering humans were not included in the search results. On March 12, 2020, the search
107 yielded a total of 14,753 records, out of which 47 duplicates were identified and removed. These
108 records were then uploaded to Covidence for further examination. Along with the database
109 search, 412 additional studies with potential relevance were discovered through expert
110 knowledge and citation chaining, and they were also uploaded to Covidence for screening.⁷

111 The final search is presented in Appendix B. The search can be rerun by copying the column of
112 queries into <https://tools.ovid.com/ovidtools/launcher.html>. This search history can be translated
113 into PubMed format as follows:

114 (vaccines[mh] OR immunization[mh] OR vaccin*[tw] or immunis*[tw] or immuniz*[tw] or
115 inoculat*[tw]) AND (intervention[tw] or interventions[tw] or treatment[tw] or treatments[tw] or
116 group[tw] or groups[tw] or trial[tw] or trials[tw] or program[tw] or programs[tw] or
117 programme[tw] or programmes[tw] or evaluat*[tiab] or experiment*[tiab]) AND (behavior[mh]
118 OR behav*[tw] OR incentiv*[tw] OR psychology[subheading] OR motivat*[tw] OR
119 motivation[mh]) NOT (animals[mh:noexp] NOT humans[mh]) AND (1990:3000[pdat])

120 Study selection

121 We considered articles focused on a behavioral insights intervention related to vaccination.
122 Behavioral insights utilize principles from psychology and economics to understand and
123 influence human behavior, informing the design of interventions and policies that align with how
124 people behave. We excluded articles that were explanatory or not based on interventions, as well
125 as those that didn't examine vaccine uptake, intent, knowledge, or attitudes as outcome measures,
126 or were not in English. We also did not include systematic reviews and meta-analyses. Two
127 reviewers independently evaluated the titles and abstracts of the selected articles for manual
128 screening to determine the final studies to be included.

129

130 Study Outcomes of interest

131 In this review, the main focus was on vaccine uptake as the primary outcome of interest, while
132 vaccine knowledge, attitudes, and intent were considered as secondary outcomes of interest.
133 Each study had its own criteria for defining the outcome. Some studies categorized outcomes
134 based on self-reports, while others relied on clinical or insurance records.⁷

135 Data extraction

136 Two coders independently reviewed the full text of all studies and extracted data using a Google
137 Form specifically designed for the data extraction. Any disagreements were resolved by
138 reviewing the study with a third judge and a decision was mutually agreed upon. We coded the
139 study characteristics including population, age, study type, inclusion of a control group, vaccine
140 type, country of the study, setting (rural vs urban), outcomes assessed, and strength of the study
141 using GRADE criteria (Appendix C). Each individual study was assessed based on the study
142 design, strengths and limitations and was graded. If there were more than 8 high GRADE studies
143 in any domain, the overall GRADE score for the domain was assigned high.

144

145 *Interventions*

146 We categorized interventions into different domains, including education campaigns (providing
147 education on vaccination, disease, and how vaccine work), on-site vaccination (providing
148 vaccine at workplace or places of worship), incentives (offering financial incentives for
149 vaccination), free vaccination (providing vaccination free of cost), institutional recommendation
150 (recommendation made by the institution that person works at especially for healthcare
151 providers), provider recommendation (recommendation by doctor/nurse), reminder and recall
152 (reminders for vaccination), message framing (persuasion messaging, gain vs loss framing of the
153 vaccine), and vaccine champion (institutional or self-appointed champion that encouraged
154 vaccination), based on their characteristics.⁷ These domains emerged thematically during
155 qualitative review of the studies included in the systematic review. Studies addressing multiple
156 domains were classified under each relevant domain.

157 The domains that we used map on the World Health Organization's Behavioral and Social
158 Drivers of Vaccination (BeSD) model⁸ as follows: What people think and feel (educational
159 campaigns), social processes (provider recommendation), motivation (vaccine champion), and
160 practical issues (on-site vaccination, free vaccination). This provides for alignment with current
161 work and will provide options for different levers to pull.

162

163 Data synthesis

164 In our primary analyses, we conducted a meta-analysis for each intervention domain using a
165 random effect model with the outcome of interest being vaccine uptake. We used the inverse
166 variance method to generate pooled odds ratios (ORs) with 95% confidence intervals.

167 We extracted odds ratios or raw numbers from individual studies to calculate a summary odds
168 ratio for each intervention's effect on vaccine uptake (self-reported or from clinical or insurance
169 records). Outcome was defined as per each study's criteria. Studies that did not provide enough
170 information for calculation of odds ratios were excluded from this meta-analysis.

171 For sensitivity analysis, we removed the outlier studies defined as a study whose 95% confidence
172 interval does not overlap with the confidence interval of the pooled effect and recalculated the
173 summary measures. We assessed the presence of publication bias using funnel plot asymmetry
174 and Egger's regression. For domains with indication of publication bias, we used the trim and fill
175 method to calculate adjusted ORs and 95% CIs. All analyses were conducted in R (version
176 R.4.1.2.) using the packages "meta"⁹ and "metasens".¹⁰

177 The study was funded by Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation. Funder played no part in study
178 design, data collection, analysis, interpretation, and manuscript preparation.

179

180

181 Results

182 After search criteria refinement, we identified 15,118 studies of which 872 were selected for full
183 text review after title and abstract screening. Of these 872 studies, 613 studies met the inclusion
184 criteria and were included in this review (Figure 1). These 613 represent 64 countries globally
185 with 37 countries being classified as Higher Income (HIC) and 27 as Low and Middle Income
186 (LMIC) countries as per the World Bank Criteria (Supplemental Figure 1). Of these 613 studies,
187 474 (77%) reported on vaccine uptake,^{11–485} 145 (24%) on vaccine attitude,

188 12,14,20,25,26,39,46,48,81,107,113,124,145,150,166–170,172,174,175,178–

189 180,184,186,187,191,195,202,216,236,262,269,273,287,288,292,293,297,300,302,304,310,317,318,320,322,323,328,329,335,341,345,346,352,3

190 53,359,363–365,368,371,383,404,426,428,435,444,450,486–559 139 (23%) on vaccine knowledge,

191 13,14,20,25,26,28,31,39,40,48,55,70,113,124,131,134,142,143,145,150,151,166–

192 169,172,175,178,180,183,186,187,189,191,195,199,202,216,218,247,256,266,276,280,282,283,288,295,300,302,304,308,311,312,322,327,343,3

193 45,346,352,356,360,386,396,403,404,425,442,486–489,492,493,498,499,501,503–507,509,510,514–516,518–521,523,526–528,531–

194 533,535,536,541,545–547,549,550,552,556,557,560–591 and 122 (20%) on vaccine intent.

195 12,13,20,36,44,48,56,64,67,75,77,81,111–

196 113,115,116,124,131,145,151,167,175,178,184,186,187,191,192,196,205,218,220,236,247,311,312,320,322,326,327,329,334,346,353,365,368,3

197 84,435,464,470,471,474,476,486,498,500–502,505,512–514,517–520,523,525,530–533,537,539–

198 541,546,551,553,554,560,562,563,565,569,572,578,588,590,592–622 Studies focused both on providers as well as

199 patients and included different target populations: Children (n=304, 49.6%), healthcare workers

200 (n=70, 11.4%), general adults (n=200, 32.6%), adults over 65 years of age (n=57, 9.3%), and

201 adults with pre-existing conditions (n=47, 7.7%).

202 Most of the studies were classified as educational campaigns (n=315, 51%)^{13,14,17,19,20,22,25,26,31–}

203 34,36,39,40,43,47,48,50,55,58–62,66,69,70,72–75,79–85,90–93,96,100–103,105,106,112,115,116,120,121,123–125,128,131,133,134,141–

204 146,148,150–154,156,160,164–169,171,172,175,178–180,182–187,189,190,196,199,201–205,207,212,215,216,219,220,222–224,231–

205 237,240,241,245–249,252,253,256–260,262,265,267,269–274,276–278,282,283,285,288,290–293,295,297–300,304,305,307,308,310–

206 312,316,317,320,322,327,334–336,338,344–347,352,355–358,360,362,363,365,366,369,370,373,377,379–383,385,386,388,389,391,399,401–

207 406,410,420,423,425,428,429,433,436,437,442,445–447,453,462,470–477,482,484,486,488,489,492,493,496,497,499,501,503–507,509–

208 511,520,524–529,531,533–536,539–541,545–550,552,557–559,561–580,583,584,586–593,595,597,602–605,614,616,619,623 followed by

209 reminder and recall (n=155, 25%)^{15,18,21,26,28–33,35,40,47,50,54,56,59,64,67,70,72,77,86,97–99,105,108,114–}

210 116,123,129,132,133,135,137–139,141,143,146–

211 148,153,160,166,174,178,179,181,188,193,194,202,206,209,210,221,225,229,232,233,238,248,253,262–264,268,271,272,276,278,279,285–

212 290,294–297,302,303,305,307,309,310,313,314,317,319,320,326,329–331,335,337,342,343,345,348,351,360,364,366,372–

213 379,381,384,385,389,393,394,397–399,403–

214 405,408,409,412,416,419,431,434,436,438,440,441,449,457,458,463,465,468,473,480,515,537,539,549,599, incentives (n=102,

215 17%)^{11,12,16,22–24,27,29,39,43,44,65,70,78,83,91,103,104,106,109,114,115,122,125–}

216 127,130,132,136,140,141,147,149,150,152,155,157,158,161,163,173,174,190,195,197,211,214,218,220,226,228,239,254,264,265,268,280,284,2

217 89–292,294,298,302,303,305,306,329–333,335,339,341,349–

218 352,362,371,372,396,400,406,414,415,417,424,427,436,437,439,448,452,460,464,516,542,543,598, message framing (n=98,

219 16%)

220 20,37,40,45,46,53,57,61,74,81,83,88,94,110,111,118,150,151,167,179,185,188,196,197,202,220,222,229,241,256,283,292,306,318,322,343,353,

221 357,359,390,421,422,425,447,451,471,484,491,494,495,498,500,502,504,509,512–514,517,518,529,530,532,538,541,542,544,545,551,553–
222 556,559,569,586,594–596,598,600,601,605–613,615,617,618,620–622, on-site vaccination (n=71, 12%)
223 20,26,33,38,39,43,49,56,72,89,94,101,113,119,121,143,150,162,176,179,190,191,208,209,217,223,224,234,244,250,254,255,264–
224 266,269,289,290,292,305,306,324,336,338,344,347,357,360–362,364,369,383,387,388,392,395,406,427,436,450,453–
225 455,461,469,474,475,479,483,490,560,581,597, free vaccination (n=63, 10%)
226 20,21,28,41,48,49,54,72,100,123,150,157,165,168,170,190,191,198,207,209,219,225,240,269,291–
227 293,306,307,314,317,318,323,336,338,341,364,366,383,387,388,392,404,417,422,430,432,436,441,443,447,448,458,459,461,462,469,477,479,4
228 90,555,599,605, provider recommendation (n=55, 9%)^{19,21,51–}
229 53,56,59,61,67,68,71,72,74,87,103,135,147,150,154,207,213,230,233,242,258,259,272,277,279,281,310,325,328,340,358,366,368,372,382,387,4
230 07,411,418,422,424,427,440,444,470,519,586,597,599,614,616, institutional recommendation (n=49, 8%)
231 22,42,43,72,95,150,154,177,190,203,243,246,257,259–261,265,267,270,271,274,275,277,278,286,291,296,304–
232 306,315,321,328,335,342,354,355,363,367,411,412,426,435,448,456,460,468,487,604, and vaccine champion (n=23, 4%;
233 table 1)^{26,84,106,113,150,223,225,227,250,253,258,269,292,301,369,379,467,474,475,522,524,547,597,598}. Below, we describe
234 the domains in detail and highlight some studies across different countries as examples of how
235 different techniques have been used to increase vaccine uptake.

236

237 Educational Campaigns

238 Educational Campaigns was the most represented domain in our review. Studies in this domain
239 came from 53 countries with 20 countries classified as LMIC (Table 1). Most (n=273, 87%) of
240 the studies were from HIC. Techniques used in this domain included informational
241 sessions/classes, lectures, workshops, informational leaflets/handouts, and online training.

242 In a cluster randomized trial in Pakistan, Andersson et al implemented three structured
243 discussions highlight vaccine uptake from a baseline survey they conducted, cost and benefits of
244 childhood vaccination and local action plans with males and females separately in the
245 intervention clusters. The intervention led to a 2-to-3-fold increase in measles and diphtheria-
246 pertussis-tetanus (DPT) vaccination.¹⁸⁶

247 In a school-based cluster randomized trial in Sweden, Grandhal et al used school nurses to
248 deliver a 30 min face to face information session on HPV, including cancer risks and HPV
249 prevention. After the intervention, the proportion of vaccinated girls in the intervention group
250 increased by 6.5 percentage points in the intervention group while there was no change in the
251 control group.³⁹¹

252 The overall GRADE score for this domain was high. There were 147 studies with enough
253 information to calculate an OR. The overall pooled OR was 2.3 (95% CI: 2.0-2.5; Figure 2). Just
254 considering studies in LMIC, the pooled OR was 2.1 (95% CI: 1.7-2.7; Figure 3). Restricting to
255 RCTs, the pooled OR was 1.7 (95% CI: 1.5-1.9; Figure 4). However, there was huge
256 heterogeneity in the studies as shown by the I^2 across all strata.

257 Reminder and Recall

258 Reminder and recall include all studies that provided a reminder for vaccination. Studies in this
259 domain represented 24 countries with 9 being LMIC (Table 1). Techniques used for reminder
260 and recall included text message reminders, telephone calls, letters, reminder services/apps and
261 appointment cards.

262 Gibson et al randomized villages in Kenya to 4 groups: control, short message service (SMS)
263 reminder only, SMS plus a 75 Kenya Shilling (KES) incentive, and SMS plus 200 KES. The

264 study found that children randomized to SMS plus 200 KES group were 1.09 times more likely
265 to be completely immunized as compared to the control group (RR: 1.09; 95%CI: 1.02 –
266 1.16).³³⁰

267 In a randomized controlled trial in Pakistan, mother-child pairs were randomized to 1 of the 4
268 groups: randomized to four study groups: redesigned card, center-based education, combined
269 intervention, and standard care. Children in the redesigned card (RR: 1.7; 95%CI: 1.5-2.0),
270 educational (RR: 1.5; 95%CI:1.3-1.8) and combined intervention (RR: 1.7; 95%CI:1.4-2.0) were
271 more likely to complete the third dose of DTP vaccine (DTP3) than children in the standard of
272 care arm.³⁷⁷

273 The overall GRADE score for this domain was high. There were 91 studies with enough
274 information to calculate an OR. The overall pooled OR was 1.7 (95%CI: 1.5-1.9; Figure 2). Just
275 considering studies in LMIC, the pooled OR was 2.0 (95%CI: 1.5-2.7; Figure 3). Restricting to
276 RCTs, the pooled OR was 1.6 (95%CI: 1.4-1.8; Figure 4). However, there was huge
277 heterogeneity in the studies as shown by the I^2 across all strata.

278

279 Incentives

280 Incentive studies represented 26 countries with 14 being LMIC (Table 1). Incentive types
281 included financial incentives, food vouchers/packages, transportation, and in-kind incentives.

282 A study from rural Nigeria randomized women to receive cash incentives if they completed their
283 tetanus toxoid vaccination into 3 groups: 5 Nigerian naira (C5), 300 naira (C300), and 800 naira
284 (C800). Investigators found that women in C300 and C800 groups were more likely to receive
285 the vaccine as compared to women in the C5 group. The study also noted that transportation
286 costs to be a significant barrier preventing women from receiving vaccines at clinic and the cash
287 incentive compensated for the transportation cost.¹²⁵

288 A randomized controlled trial in 2 inner-city health services in Sydney, Australia randomized
289 Serologically confirmed HBV-susceptible people who inject drugs to receive 30 Australian
290 Dollars cash following receipt of vaccine doses two and three of HBV vaccine or standard care.
291 The completion rate for all 3 doses in the intervention arm was 87% compared to 66% in the
292 control arm.²⁷

293 The overall GRADE score for this domain was high. There were 51 studies with enough
294 information to calculate an OR. The overall pooled OR was 2.3 (95%CI: 1.9-2.8; Figure 2). Just
295 considering studies in LMIC, the pooled OR was 1.8 (95%CI: 1.0-3.2; Figure 3). Restricting to
296 RCTs, the pooled OR was 1.5 (95%CI: 1.1-2.4; Figure 4). However, there was huge
297 heterogeneity in the studies as shown by the I^2 across all strata.

298

299 Message Framing

300 Studies in this domain represented 27 countries with 3 being LMIC (Table 1). Modalities used
301 included persuasive messages, gain vs loss framed messages, assertive messages, and self-
302 affirmation.

303 Chien used a 2 by 3 factorial design to assess the impact of gain vs loss framed messages and
304 color configuration in online banners on persuasion for flu vaccination. The study found that loss

305 framed messages using white text on red background improved persuasion compared to gain
306 framed messages.⁵³⁸

307 A randomized controlled trial in India provided mothers face-to-face information on the benefits
308 of tetanus vaccine. The trial had 3 arms: mothers in the first arm received information framed as
309 a gain (e.g., the child is less likely to get tetanus and more likely to be healthy if vaccinated),
310 mothers in the second arm received information framed in terms of a loss (e.g., the child is more
311 likely to get tetanus and suffer ill health if not vaccinated), and the third arm was the control
312 group. The pooled RR for the 2 intervention groups was 1.7 (95%CI: 1.3-2.3) for full
313 immunization. There was no difference between the 2 intervention arms.¹¹⁸

314 The overall GRADE score for this domain was high. There were 15 studies with enough
315 information to calculate an OR. The overall pooled OR was 1.9 (95%CI: 1.5-2.4; Figure 2). As
316 there was only 1 study with information to calculate an OR from LMIC, LMIC specific pooled
317 OR was not calculated. Restricting to RCTs, the pooled OR was 1.5 (95%CI: 1.2-2.0; Figure 4).
318 However, there was huge heterogeneity in the studies as shown by the I^2 across all strata.

319 Gain vs loss framed messages did not differ in improving vaccine uptake.

320

321 On-site Vaccination

322 The 71 studies in this domain came from 25 countries of which 11 were LMIC (Table 1).
323 Vaccination sites included churches/places of worship, schools, workplaces, hospitals/local
324 clinics and community centers.

325 Daniels et al provided on-site vaccination at faith-based institutions (churches) in African
326 American and Latinx communities in a cluster randomized controlled trial in California, USA.
327 The study found a difference of between 31 and 34 percentage points for pneumococcal and
328 influenza vaccination uptake in intervention vs control groups.¹⁴³

329 A teaching hospital in Nigeria implemented a vaccine program where free vaccinations were
330 provided on-site to the hospital staff. The level of participation among healthcare workers was
331 high, with 91.9% of the target group receiving at least one dose of the Hepatitis B vaccine.⁴⁹⁰

332 The overall GRADE score for this domain was high. There were 23 studies with enough
333 information to calculate an OR. The overall pooled OR was 2.9 (95%CI: 2.3-3.7; Figure 2). Just
334 considering studies in LMIC, the pooled OR was 2.4 (95%CI: 1.0-5.8; Figure 3). Restricting to
335 RCTs, the pooled OR was 1.5 (95%CI: 1.2-2.0; Figure 4). However, there was huge
336 heterogeneity in the studies as shown by the I^2 across all strata.

337

338 Free Vaccination

339 Studies in this domain came from 22 countries of which 5 were LMIC (Table 1).

340 In Colombia, Bogota Health Department collaborated with a foundation to provide a free multi-
341 dose vaccination program for Hepatitis B among the female and transexual sex workers. The
342 study found a higher adherence rate (37.7%) for the vaccination program among these
343 marginalized communities compared to other programs.¹⁹⁸

344 In a cluster randomized controlled trial in France, Launay et al evaluated the impact of free on-
345 site Hepatitis B vaccinations, training on epidemiology and risk-factors or both for healthcare
346 workers on HBV vaccination acceptability in high-risk adults consulting in 12 free and
347 anonymous HIV and hepatitis B/C testing centres. The study showed that training and free on-
348 site vaccine availability was more effective than free on-site vaccine availability alone (RR: 1.14;
349 95%CI: 1.02-1.26) to increase vaccination acceptability resulting in a 29.8 percentage point
350 increase in vaccine coverage. There was no effect from healthcare worker training alone.²⁴⁰

351 The overall GRADE score for this domain was high. There were 33 studies with enough
352 information to calculate an OR. The overall pooled OR was 2.6 (95%CI: 2.0-3.2; Figure 2). Just
353 considering studies in LMIC, the pooled OR was 1.5 (95%CI: 0.7-3.1; Figure 3). Restricting to
354 RCTs, the pooled OR was 2.0 (95%CI: 1.1-3.7; Figure 4). However, there was huge
355 heterogeneity in the studies as shown by the I^2 across all strata.

356

357 Provider Recommendation

358 The 55 studies in this domain came from 14 countries of which 3 were LMIC (India, Nigeria,
359 and Sudan) (Table 1). Providers included family practitioners, nurse practitioners, community
360 clinic staff, immunization nurses and pharmacists, while techniques included standing orders.

361 Ansari et al report on a study conducted in India where an intervention was implemented to
362 promote polio vaccination among resistant families. A team of healthcare workers conducted
363 house to house visits identifying families who refused to give polio drops to the children. These
364 families were again visited by medical interns, who provided health education and vaccine
365 promotion/ recommendation. Families still resistant to vaccination were visited once more by
366 another team. Of the resistant families, 79.3% were persuaded to receive the polio vaccinations
367 after two rounds of visits.³⁸²

368 Three hundred and forty-six unvaccinated patients with inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) were
369 randomized to either routine clinical care or intervention group receiving additional education by
370 a nurse with help of an information brochure and vaccination card in Belgium. Eight months
371 later, 33% of intervention group versus 6% of control group had followed vaccination
372 recommendations.¹⁵⁴

373 The overall GRADE score for this domain was high. There were 33 studies with enough
374 information to calculate an OR. The overall pooled OR was 3.4 (95%CI: 2.5-4.6; Figure 2). Just
375 considering studies in LMIC, the pooled OR was 2.4 (95%CI: 1.2-4.6; Figure 3). Restricting to
376 RCTs, the pooled OR was 2.1 (95%CI: 1.5-2.8; Figure 4). However, there was huge
377 heterogeneity in the studies as shown by the I^2 across all strata.

378

379 Institutional Recommendation

380 Of the 49 studies in the domain, 43 (88%) were from HIC countries representing 10 countries.
381 (Table 1). Techniques used included mandatory declination, vaccine mandates, supervisory
382 reminders, and visual cues.

383 Belcher report on a randomized controlled trial in Seattle with 3 interventions: 1) a physician-
384 oriented education and motivation model with periodic feedback about performance, 2) a patient
385 education model with mailed informative brochure, and 3) a health promotion clinic. Only the

386 use of the health promotion clinic model was found to increase prevention rates (including
387 vaccination rates) three-folds and had a sustained impact over five years.²⁴⁶

388 In San Antonio, Texas, a study done on healthcare workers to improve influenza vaccination
389 rates intervened using support of leadership, distribution of vaccine kits, grand rounds
390 presentations and email and phone reminders. The study found a significant increase in
391 vaccination rates among the staff going from 58.8% to 76.6%.²⁵⁹

392 The overall GRADE score for this domain was high. There were 10 studies with enough
393 information to calculate an OR. The overall pooled OR was 2.6 (95% CI: 2.2-3.2; Figure 2). As
394 there was only 1 study with information to calculate an OR from LMIC, LMIC specific pooled
395 OR was not calculated. Restricting to RCTs, the pooled OR was 2.0 (95% CI: 1.2-3.3; Figure 4).
396 However, there was huge heterogeneity in the studies as shown by the I^2 across all strata.

397

398 Vaccine Champion

399 There were 6 countries represented in this domain with Nigeria being the only LMIC. Twenty-
400 one (91%) of the studies were from HIC (Table 1). Champions included nurses, peers,
401 community leaders, religious leaders and celebrities.

402 Slaunwhite et al report on a study from Canada where health workers were recruited to be
403 champions to motivate members of their work units to get vaccinated against influenza. These
404 champions were provided a brief training session to increase awareness. The results showed a
405 significant increase in vaccine rates among the units with vaccine champions.³⁰¹

406 In a randomized controlled trial in Georgia, USA, expecting mothers were randomized to an
407 intervention bracket including identification of a vaccine champion, provider-to-patient talking
408 points, educational brochures, posters, lapel buttons, and iPads loaded with a patient-centered
409 tutorial. The rates of influenza and Tetanus vaccines were higher among the intervention groups
410 as compared to the control group.²⁵⁸

411 The overall GRADE score for this domain was high. There were 9 studies with enough
412 information to calculate an OR. The overall pooled OR was 2.5 (95% CI: 1.8-3.5; Figure 2). As
413 there was only 1 study with information to calculate an OR from LMIC, LMIC specific pooled
414 OR was not calculated. Restricting to RCTs, the pooled OR was 1.9 (95% CI: 1.2-3.0; Figure 4).
415 However, there was huge heterogeneity in the studies as shown by the I^2 across all strata.

416

417 Interventions with limited evidence of effectiveness

418 Our review shows that incentives need to be valued by participants for them to be effective. In
419 affluent or high-income communities, incentives did not show a significant increase in vaccine
420 uptake amongst healthcare workers.

421 Decisional aids and self-assessments amongst Educational Campaigns were shown to be less
422 effective in improving vaccine uptake. Educational messages also need to be paired with self-
423 efficacy or response-efficacy messages as on their own, educational messages did not improve
424 vaccine uptake.

425 Studies did not evaluate vaccine uptake in quality improvement programs generally. Limited
426 available evidence did not show quality improvement programs increase vaccine uptake.

427 Sensitivity Analysis

428 In sensitivity analysis, we recalculated the ORs and 95% CIs (Figure 5) for all studies in domains
429 that were Graded high. There was no difference in ORs for RCTs and high-GRADE studies
430 (Figures 4 and 5). This is to be expected as one of the grading criteria for a study to be Graded
431 high is RCT.

432 Supplement Figure 2 shows the ORs and 95% CI for RCTs conducted in LMICs. The results are
433 comparable to when restricting to studies conducted in LMICs (Figures 3 and 6).

434

435 Sensitivity Analysis and Publication Bias

436 In sensitivity analysis, we removed the outlier studies in each domain and recalculated the
437 pooled ORs and 95% CI (Supplement Table 2). The ORs and 95% CI were very similar to those
438 calculated from the full study set however the I^2 improved for all domains.

439 We assessed the presence of publication bias using visual representation of the studies (funnel
440 plots; Supplement Figure 3) and Egger's test (Supplement Table 3). Based on these analyses, we
441 suspected presence of publication bias for 4 domains. We used trim and fill with outliers
442 removed to recalculate the ORs and 95% CI to adjust for the possibility of publication bias. The
443 adjusted pooled ORs were Education 2.1 (95% CI: 2.0-2.2), Provider Recommendation 3.4
444 (95% CI: 2.8-4.1), Institutional Recommendation 2.4 (95% CI: 1.8-3.1), and Vaccine Champion 2.0
445 (95% CI: 1.4-2.9). There was no indication of publication bias when we restricted our analysis to
446 just RCTs (Supplement Table 3).

447

448 **Discussion**

449 Our results show that behavioral interventions can improve vaccine uptake considerably. All
450 domains that we examined improved vaccine uptake with the highest effect size associated with
451 Provider Recommendation (OR: 3.4; Domain: motivation) and Onsite vaccination (OR: 2.9;
452 Domain: practical issues).

453 Healthcare workers are the most trusted source of information for health-related knowledge
454 including vaccination as shown in multiple studies. Hence, if a healthcare provider recommends
455 an action such as vaccination, individuals are more likely to adopt it increasing vaccine uptake.
456 A previous systematic review and meta-analysis also demonstrated a strong and consistent
457 association between provider communication and HPV vaccination initiation, completion, and
458 follow-through.⁶²⁴ Standing orders that authorize health care personnel to assess a patient's
459 immunization status and administer vaccinations according to a pre-approved protocol have
460 shown improvement in vaccine uptake both individually and when linked to reminder and recall.
461 The evidence of their effectiveness is based on mostly programmatic studies/retrospective
462 reviews.

463 Onsite vaccination provides easy access to vaccines near the patient, eliminating extra effort on
464 their part, travel time and cost, leading to increased vaccine uptake. Onsite vaccination can also
465 be combined with free vaccination further reducing the cost for the patient.

466 We found that educational interventions specifically designed to cater to specific target
467 populations were effective in improving vaccine knowledge associated with improved vaccine

468 uptake. This indicates a need for specifically designed campaigns for selected populations after
469 identifying their needs to improve vaccine uptake.

470 When considering reminder and recall, both patients and provider reminder and recall systems
471 are important. Reminder and recall interventions combined with other interventions such as
472 incentives and education are more likely to increase vaccine uptake and should be offered as a
473 package of interventions. Similarly, financial incentives both at the level of the provider and at
474 the level of the consumer can improve vaccine uptake. There also seems to be a dose-response
475 relationship between the amount of incentive and vaccine uptake. Each implementing region will
476 need to consider the optimum number of financial incentives for their settings.

477 Message framing interventions can improve vaccine knowledge and acceptance depending on
478 the other variables in the study and use of appropriately framed messages for target populations.
479 However, some types of message framing can have negative effects on vaccine acceptance.
480 Hence, such interventions need to be considered carefully before deployment and can be
481 combined into a package of interventions combining other domains together.

482 Few of our included studies focused on message framing, institutional recommendation, and
483 vaccine champions from LMICs that look at vaccine uptake as an outcome. The evidence from
484 HICs for these domains is strong for vaccine uptake but further studies need to be conducted
485 from LMIC to evaluate these interventions in that context. The quality of studies from HICs and
486 LMICs was generally similar. However, the overall number of studies from HIC (n=523) was
487 almost 6 times higher and many LMICs were not represented. This points to a need to conduct
488 and publish more studies in LMIC settings as context may influence both behavioral
489 interventions and their association with vaccine uptake.

490 Strengths of our study include a comprehensive review of the behavioral interventions focused
491 on vaccine uptake. To our knowledge, this is the first systematic review and meta-analysis on the
492 subject. Our search strategy was highly sensitive and inclusive, and we are confident that we
493 captured a majority of the studies published on the topic in our review. We assessed the quality
494 of the studies using a tool that is widely used for assessing quality of evidence and making
495 recommendations and should be readily interpretable by different stakeholders including the
496 policymakers. All domains had multiple high-quality studies resulting in a GRADE of high for
497 each domain.

498 Limitations of our work include that not all studies provided enough information for calculating
499 a summary measure for vaccine uptake and hence were not included in the meta-analysis. These
500 studies were included in the systematic review. There was considerable heterogeneity in each
501 domain. This is expected as the interventions considered have been used for different populations
502 in many different settings and have been examined using a variety of study designs.

503 Additionally, while our study aimed to provide a comprehensive review, there is potential
504 heterogeneity and publication bias from high-income countries which could impact the
505 generalizability of the findings, particularly in LMICs. We provide effect estimates by different
506 settings and study design as sensitivity analyses. Although we searched a single database for
507 studies, we used a comprehensive search strategy with robust subject indexing that was
508 sufficiently sensitive in capturing the relevant studies. Further, to mitigate this, we assessed
509 publication bias and corrected for it using a scientifically robust method (Trim and Fill) and
510 present the corrected ORs for domains with publication bias indicated.

511

512 **Conclusions/Policy Recommendations**

513 Our results show that behavioral interventions can be used to increase vaccine uptake in most
514 settings, particularly provider recommendations and on-site vaccination. With on-site
515 vaccination, it is important to determine the appropriate timings for vaccination spots and
516 establish rapport with local community leaders to promote vaccination sites. For provider
517 recommendations, educational campaigns should be implemented among health care workers
518 and it is crucial to establish consistent and factual process of provider recommendation with on-
519 going monitoring, including reminder and recall and incentives. Overall, provider
520 recommendations and on-site vaccination should be employed along with other interventions to
521 increase vaccination rates globally. Our results systematically expand upon the findings of the
522 previous reviews conducted by Brewer et al⁵ and Oh et al⁶²⁴ and provide additional evidence
523 including quantitative assessment of strategies to increase vaccine uptake rates.

524

525

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Figure 1. Studies included and excluded at each stage of review process.

2245 **Figure 2.** Forrest Plot showing ORs and respective 95% CIs for all studies included in the meta-
 2246 analysis by domains
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2249 **Figure 3.** Forrest Plot showing ORs and respective 95% CIs for all studies from LMICs included
 2250 in the meta-analysis by domains
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2254 **Figure 4.** Forrest Plot showing ORs and respective 95% CIs for all RCTs included in the meta-
 2255 analysis by domains
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2259 **Figure 5.** Forrest Plot showing ORs and respective 95% CIs for all high-GRADE studies included
 2260 in the meta-analysis by domains
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2264 **Table 1: Distribution of studies included in the systematic review by domain and income**
 2265 **status of the countries**

Domains	Total Studies	Studies from HIC	No. of HIC represented	Studies from LMICs	No. of LMICs represented
Educational Campaigns	315	273	33	42	20
Reminder and Recall	155	136	16	19	9
Incentives	102	80	12	22	14
Message Framing	98	94	20	5	3
On-site vaccination	71	57	14	14	11
Free vaccination	63	54	17	9	5
Provider Recommendation	55	51	11	4	3
Institutional Recommendation	49	43	10	6	4
Vaccine Champion	23	21	5	2	1

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Supplement

APPENDIX A

Approaches to identify final search strategy

Vaccination concept	exp vaccines/ or exp immunization/ or (vaccin* or immunis* or immuniz* or inoculat*).mp.			
Intervention study concept	(intervention or interventions or treatment or treatments or group or groups or trial or trials or program or programs or programme or programmes).mp. or (evaluat* or experiment*).ti,ab,kw.			
Date limit	1990-current			
Behavioral approaches concept	Operationalization I	Operationalization II	Operationalization III	Operationalization IV
Description	An early approach, using many potentially relevant search terms	Selected terms (based on their performance retrieving records in the validation set)	Fewer terms	Ultra-streamlined approach
Operationalizations of the behavioral approach concept	exp behavior/ or behav*.mp. or (incentiv* or presumptive communication or interpersonal communication or decision analysis or default).mp. or motivation/ or psychology.fs. or communication.mp . or ((risk or presumptive or interpersonal) adj1 communication).mp. or communication/ or exp communication/ or health	exp behavior/ or behav*.mp. or incentiv*.mp. or motivat*.mp. or motivation/ or psychology.fs. or communication.mp. or exp communication/ or (intent or intention*).mp. or (attitude or attitudes).mp. or exp attitude/ or (risk or risks).mp. or decision making.mp. or exp decision making/ or	exp behavior/ or behav*.mp. or incentiv*.mp. or psychology.fs. or	exp behavior/ or behav*.mp.

	<p>communication/ or health literacy/ or (intent or intention*).mp. or intention/ or (persuad* or persuasi*).mp. or persuasive communication/ or narrative*.mp. or (message framing or messaging or health message*).mp. or affect.mp. or affect/ or social process*.mp. or (risk perception or (risk* adj2 (perception* or perceiv*))).mp. or (default or defaults).mp. or decision-making.mp. or (presumptive or participatory).mp. or (attitude or attitudes).mp. or exp attitude/ or attitude/ or attitude of health personnel/ or exp attitude to health/ or patient acceptance of health care/ or exp</p>	<p>(refus* or hesita* or delay* or activism or activist* or accept*).mp.</p>		
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	<p>patient acceptance of health care/ or (risk or risks).mp. or ((risk or risks) adj2 assess*).mp. or exp risk/ or risk/ or risk assessment/ or social network analys*.mp. or (pro-vaccin* or anti-vaccin* or antivaccin*).mp. or (pro-vax* or anti-vax* or antivax*).mp. or anti-vaccination movement/ or decision making.mp. or exp decision making/ or exp choice behavior/ or decision making/ or social norms/ or social norm*.mp. or exp reward/ or motivation/ or reward*.mp. or cognition/ or cognition.mp. or exp cognition/ or (intervention or interventions or</p>			
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	evaluation*).mp. or program evaluation/ or ((behavioral or behavioural) adj1 (economics or insight*).mp. or ((behavior* or behaviour*) adj1 change theory).mp. or (behav* change adj1 (theor* or model*).mp.			
Records retrieved by the behavioral concept*	7931390	6486942	3145763	26611721
Screening workload – union of vaccination, intervention study, and behavioral concepts, with date limit*	84363	59983	16112	14125
Performance retrieving validation articles available in Medline**	34/34 100%	31/33 91%	28/34 82%	19/34 56%
Comments	Sensitive, but not feasible	Sensitive, but not feasible	Feasible and relatively sensitive	Feasible but not sensitive

2271 * The table presents information from testing on January 10, 2020. The same searches rerun
2272 today would retrieve additional records.

2273 ** As of January 2020, our validation article set included 34 articles available in Medline. As the
2274 testing process continued, we added additional articles to the validation set.

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APPENDIX B

2277

Final search Results

Ovid MEDLINE(R) ALL <1946 to March 11, 2020>		
Search history sorted by search number ascending		
#	Searches	Results
1	[concept 1 -- vaccines]	0
2	exp vaccines/	225103
3	exp immunization/	172624
4	(vaccin* or immunis* or immuniz* or inoculat*).mp.	569359
5	or/2-4	587159
6	[concept 2 -- intervention studies]	0
7	(intervention or interventions or treatment or treatments or group or groups or trial or trials or program or programs or programme or programmes).mp.	9225213
8	(evaluat* or experiment*).ti,ab,kw.	5218032
9	or/7-8	12097558
10	[concept 3 -- behavioral approaches]	0
11	exp behavior/	1772286
12	behav*.mp.	1675707
13	incentiv*.mp.	35679
14	psychology.fs.	1038196
15	motivat*.mp.	167355
16	motivation/	65829
17	or/11-16	3250486
18	5 and 9 and 17	18089
19	limit 18 to yr="1990 -Current"	16917
20	19 not (animals not humans).sh.	14753

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2280 **APPENDIX C**
 2281 **The Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE)**
 2282 **approach**

2283 GRADE approach assesses the quality of evidence and strength of recommendation in healthcare
 2284 settings and is widely used during systematic review and clinical guidelines development
 2285 processes.

2286 The approach has 2 components:

2287 1) Quality of evidence

2288 Quality of evidence is rated as follows:

Grade	Description
High	There is a lot of confidence that the true effect lies close to that of the estimated effect.
Moderate	There is moderate confidence in the estimated effect: The true effect is likely to be close to the estimated effect, but there is a possibility that it is substantially different.
Low	There is limited effect in the estimated effect: The true effect might be substantially different from the estimated effect.
Very Low	There is very little confidence in the estimated effect: The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimated effect.

2289
 2290 GRADE judgments refer not to individual studies but to a body of evidence. The quality of
 2291 evidence for each patient important outcome is assessed based on study design and strengths and
 2292 limitations present across the body of evidence. Randomized trials provide, in general, stronger
 2293 evidence than observational studies. Rigorous observational studies provide stronger evidence
 2294 than uncontrolled case series. In the GRADE approach, randomized trials without important
 2295 limitations constitute high quality evidence. Observational studies without special strengths or
 2296 important limitations constitute low quality evidence.

2297 Limitations to consider:

- 2298 a) Risk of bias (study limitations) including lack of allocation concealment; lack of
 2299 blinding, particularly if outcomes are subjective and their assessment highly susceptible
 2300 to bias; a large loss to follow-up; failure to adhere to an intention to treat analysis;
 2301 stopping early for benefit; or selective reporting of outcomes
- 2302 b) Inconsistent results across studies
- 2303 c) Indirectness of evidence
- 2304 d) Imprecision of estimate
- 2305 e) Publication bias

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 2307 Strengths to consider:

- 2308 a) Size of the effect estimate. Larger the magnitude of effect, stronger the evidence
- 2309 b) Identification of bias working against the treatment effect
- 2310 c) Presence of dose-response gradient

2311 GRADE starts with the study design to rate the quality of evidence and then rates it downwards
 2312 or upwards depending on the limitations and strengths as shown in the table below:

A summary of GRADE's approach to rating quality of evidence

Study design	Initial quality of a body of evidence		Lower if	Higher if	Quality of a body of evidence
Randomized trials	High	→	Risk of Bias -1 Serious -2 Very serious Inconsistency -1 Serious -2 Very serious Indirectness -1 Serious -2 Very serious Imprecision -1 Serious -2 Very serious Publication bias -1 Likely -2 Very likely	Large effect +1 Large +2 Very large Dose response +1 Evidence of a gradient All plausible residual confounding +1 Would reduce a demonstrated effect +1 Would suggest a spurious effect if no effect was observed	High (four plus: ⊕⊕⊕⊕) Moderate (three plus: ⊕⊕⊕○) Low (two plus: ⊕⊕○○) Very low (one plus: ⊕○○○)
Observational studies	Low	→			

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2) Strength of recommendation

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GRADE rates strength of recommendation either as strong or weak. Strong recommendation is made when desirable effects certainly outweigh undesirable effects (or vice versa) while a weak recommendation is made when there is more uncertainty present.

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Things to consider while rating strength of recommendation:

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a) Quality of evidence

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b) Uncertainty about the balance between desirable and undesirable effects

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c) Uncertainty or variability in values and preferences

2323

d) Uncertainty about whether the intervention represents a wise use of resources

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Supplement Figure 1. Geographical Distribution of Countries includes in the Systematic Review

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2369 **Supplement Figure 2.** Forrest Plot showing ORs and respective 95% CIs for all RCTs from
 2370 LMICs included in the meta-analysis by domains

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Supplement Figure 3. Funnel Plots showing distribution of ORs and SEs of all studies by domains

a) Educational Campaigns

b) On-site Vaccination

c) Incentives

d) Free Vaccination

e) Institutional Recommendation

f) Provider Recommendation

g) Reminder & Recall

h) Message Framing

i) Vaccine Champion

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Supplemental Table 1. Approaches to identify final search strategy.

Vaccination concept	exp vaccines/ or exp immunization/ or (vaccin* or immunis* or immuniz* or inoculat*).mp.			
Intervention study concept	(intervention or interventions or treatment or treatments or group or groups or trial or trials or program or programs or programme or programmes).mp. or (evaluat* or experiment*).ti,ab,kw.			
Date limit	1990-current			
Behavioral approaches concept	Operationalization I	Operationalization II	Operationalization III	Operationalization IV
Description	An early approach, using many potentially relevant search terms	Selected terms (based on their performance retrieving records in the validation set)	Fewer terms	Ultra-streamlined approach
Records retrieved by the behavioral concept*	7931390	6486942	3145763	26611721
Screening workload *	84363	59983	16112	14125
Performance retrieving validation articles available in Medline**	34/34 100%	31/34 91%	28/34 82%	19/34 56%

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* The table presents information from testing on January 10, 2020. The same searches rerun

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today would retrieve additional records.

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** As of January 2020, our validation article set included 34 articles available in Medline. As the

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testing process continued, we added additional articles to the validation set.

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2382 **Supplement Table 2.** ORs and respective 95% CIs for all studies included in the meta-analysis
 2383 by domains after removing the outlier studies

	N (meta)	OR (95% CI)	I-square (%)
Education Campaign	77	2.1 (2.0-2.2)	40.3
On-site Vaccination	10	2.7 (2.2-3.5)	59.4
Incentives	20	2.3 (2.1-2.6)	72.5
Free Vaccination	15	2.3 (1.9-2.7)	89.9
Institutional Recommendation	4	2.4 (1.8-3.1)	60.0
Provider Recommendation	18	3.1 (2.6-3.8)	77.6
Reminder and Recall	52	1.6 (1.5-1.7)	38.6
Message Framing	13	1.5 (1.3-1.8)	39.2
Vaccine Champion	5	2.0 (1.4-2.9)	71.7

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Supplement Table 3. Results of Egger’s Regression for all studies and RCTs included in the meta-analysis by domains

	All Studies		RCTs	
	Intercept (95% CI)	p-value	Intercept (95% CI)	p-value
Education Campaign	4.4 (2.6-6.2)	<0.01	0.9 (-0.7-2.5)	0.25
On-site Vaccination	3.7 (-2.4-9.9)	0.25	0.7 (-5.0-6.5)	0.81
Incentives	-1.6 (-5.1-1.8)	0.35	-2.8 (-8.1-2.4)	0.30
Free Vaccination	2.6 (-2.1-7.2)	0.29	-3.8 (-17.1-9.6)	0.60
Institutional Recommendation	6.4 (4.0-8.9)	<0.01	3.0 (-0.4-5.7)	0.15
Provider Recommendation	3.9 (0.5-7.3)	0.03	1.0 (-1.0-3.1)	0.37
Reminder and Recall	-0.6 (-2.3-1.2)	0.52	1.6 (0.02-3.3)	0.05
Message Framing	1.0 (-0.3-2.2)	0.15	0.5 (-1.1-2.1)	0.56
Vaccine Champion	4.7 (0.9-8.6)	0.04	2.3 (0.1-4.6)	0.14

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2393 **Supplement Table 4.** Adjusted ORs and respective 95% CIs using Trim and Fill method for outlier
 2394 studies removed for all studies included in the meta-analysis by domains
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	N	OR (95% CI)	I-square (%)
Education Campaign	77 (0 added studies)	2.1 (2.0-2.2)	40.3
Institutional Recommendation	4 (0 added studies)	2.4 (1.8-3.1)	60
Provider Recommendation	20 (2 added studies)	3.4 (2.8-4.1)	77.7
Vaccine Champion	5 (0 added studies)	2.0 (1.4-2.9)	71.7

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